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Introduction:

The institution of SEZ's an offshoot of SAP in India since 1991. The passage of SEZ Act in place of PEZ in 2005 has come as an encouragement for state governments to attract private industries in to their states. The period after fin the last two years) witnessed fast growth of them (404 formally approved by 2007) in several states but skewed towards few slates like Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Gujarat, Andhra Pradesh. Their growth has also witnessed controversies over the way the act is misused, stiff peoples' resistance, protests on the grounds of improper EIA, inadequate compensation, loss of fertile soils, livelihoods and displacement and poor rehabilitation etc and thus it has become a hot bed of intense debate. In this background, this paper addresses to some of the socio- political and economic dimensions attendant with SEZs. It touches mostly the operational issues vis-a -vis the initial response profile by taking few cases for examination.

The study shows that the states in forefront of reform process have been promoting more SEZs than other states, thus leading to regional inequity. It further reveals that more land is allotted than required for business allowing scope for real estate deals. An important source of troubles has been a complete and utter -secrecy of the SEZ.s. Some times even the invocation of RTI is of no avail to get the facts. The process and production nature are also inequities and they profit the rich more at the cost of poor and marginalized. Rehabilitation and resettlement have acquired greater dimension and has become a source of people getting discontent, restive and thereby serious protests from locals and political parties, The loss of fertile land, livelihoods, displacement and inadequate resettlement has been of high order. The improper and misleading EIA arc challenged. Controversial clearances flouting the norms have been the order than exception.

Export Promoting Zones (EPZs) are an international phenomenon that has been catching up fast enmeshing many countries with increased number under the force of globalization and the new paradigm of development [1]. In India, the later part of post-reform period has also witnessed an emerging phenomenon of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and by 2007 the approvals went up to 404 [2] and much more are in the pipeline in the very recent past. EPZs, which were meant for promotion of export- oriented units have given place for SEZ's in 2000. The passage of SEZ Act in 2005 with more lucrative provisions has come in to operation since February 2006 and the approvals shoot up to 212 covering 21 states within six months' time. The main intention has been to attract industrial private capital and FDI and increase the direct employment to about 5 lakh people. The main features of the Act include: comprehensive framework involving all the stakeholders, to provide expeditious and single window clearance mechanisms and encourage orderly development with centralized control and supervision.

The growth of SEZs has also witnessed concerns and controversies over the Act and the way the Act is misused, stiff peoples' resistance, protests on the grounds of improper EIA, inadequate compensation, loss of fertile soils, livelihoods and displacement and poor rehabilitation etc and thus it has become a hot bed of intense debate among the cross section of the society on the socio-economic and political impacts.

Objective and Methodology:

In this background, this paper addresses to some of the socio- political, economic and ecological dimensions attendant with SEZs. It touches mostly the operational issues vis-a -vis the initial response profile by taking few cases for examination. In view of small period of its existence, the full impact could not be analyzed in this paper.

The Progress of SEZs:

The initial response as well as the growth in terms of number is quite good. Their number has gone up to 212 in the first six-month period and another 192 in another six months. Enthused by this macro climate, various states have invoked this Act to promote private industries in their respective states. There is competition for investments among states [3] [4]. However, few states share relatively more. The trend is

skewed towards few industrialized states like Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Gujarat, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh. It may be seen that the states in the forefront of reform process have been promoting more SHZs than other states. Already, five states share 60 percent of investments [5] and the uneven distribution of SEZs may further deepen the regional inequity and uneven growth. This goes against the spirit of balanced regional growth and the principles of localization of industries.

Under the SEZ policy, the state acquires the land, provides water, power and such other infrastructure facilities besides several tax concessions and exemptions to attract industries in to. the state. They invoke Land Acquisition Act of 1894 for acquisition of land for SEZs.in the name of social good and transfer them to private investors.

Profile of Select SEZs:

A brief profile of select SEZs is presented in Chart 1 with a view to identify the problems faced by SEZs [6].; The area for acquisition varies widely from about 100 ha to 1000 ha depending on the nature of the project and the scale. It shows that the problems are multifarious and vary in intensity. The major problem is land acquisition, loss of fertile land, less compensation, environmental issues, lack of environmental clearance, displacement, resettlement and lack of prior intimation and the discussion is focused on these issues.

Land Acquired More than Required:

Due to favorable industrial climate, the policy of SEZ and competition among the states has given the desired result in attracting domestic capital as well as FDI and the sophisticated technology. However, the state provides for "zones on demand" i.e., zones are created at the behest of investment capital that is more speculative. Experience shows that investors are showing more land than required. For example, Gorai SEZ in north Mumbai in the recreation and tourism development zone, has initially proposed an SEZ covering 5, 740 ha in lug villages and subsequently reduced 101000 ha and finally to 110 ha.[7] Similar is the case with many more SEZs such as Nandigram, Singur, POSCO [8]. By 2007, the approved SEZ projects involve an area of 54,280 ha land. It is generally observed that only less than 50 per cent is used for productive purposes [9] and the rest can be used for real estate purpose [10]. Thus, one can notice misuse of land for real-estate. Another issue surrounding SEZs is loss of agricultural land to non- agricultural purposes that has serious implications for food security in the country [11] if the present trend continues.

Economic Dimensions:

The nature and composition of products range widely but they are more of rich -centered; for example, Nano cars, chemicals, tourism etc., than to meet the basic needs and therefore, leads to inequities across people and between SEZ and Non-SEZ industries. Moreover, they profit the rich more at the cost of poor and marginalized. The overriding concern is profit orientation and various sops offered in the forms of free services, tax concessions/ exemptions etc, will only encourage relocation of industries to gain the advantages. Thus, it benefits the firms than percolation to the poor. Moreover, these sops will lead to the revenue loss of high order to the state at least in the short-run. As the modern foreign technology is more automatic and computerized and calls for highly technical workers, the employment potential for locals is quite limited.

Ecological Dimensions:

An important fall out of the SEZs is the imminent displacement of thousands of people and livelihoods in the countryside where the SEZs are slated to come up. Normally, there is no mention of number of people to be displaced by the zones. The SEZ concept promotes land development without directly addressing impacts on cultivable land and the natural resource base.

Rehabilitation and resettlement have acquired greater dimension and has become a source of people getting discontent, restive and thereby serious protests from locals. The loss of fertile land, livelihoods, displacement and inadequate resettlement has been of high order. The improper and misleading EIA are normally challenged. Controversial clearances by the concerned authorities flouting the norms have been the order than exception.

Socio-Political Dimensions:

The state initiates the land acquisition process under 1894 Land Acquisition Act under 'greater

common good.' Transparency lacks in notification and is generally kept as secret. Consent is obtained through coercion [12]. The recent cases of Nandigram, Singur and POSCO have brought such instances to the surface. An important source of troubles has been a complete and utter secrecy of the SEZs. Some times, even the invocation of RTI is of no avail to get the facts. Thus, we see usually coercive intrusion of the state in the lives and livelihoods of locals. This state domain through colonial legislation normally supersedes the right of the people to determine their own future that is conferred through 73rd Constitutional Amendment (1992) and Scheduled Areas Act of 1996. In certain states, they have made different land acquisition laws for SEZs.

Conclusion:

The review shows that SEZs dazzle with foreign investment and technological booms; but they also have a dark side that is rarely recognized. What is happening in SEZs today, can be seen as progress in so far as aggregate investment and income generation is concerned socially and in the inclusive development it is nothing but regression. The externalities impinge heavily on the economy and unless a mechanism is devised to internalize them, the tempo may not be sustained in the long run. The lessons from various countries' particularly from the Chinese experience are relevant for India, where "zone fever" [e] has already taking roots.

The Indian state has long history of displacement for the "greater common good" and failure of rehabilitation and resettlement. The observation of NRRP in 2007 is an apt one in this respect and needs recognition and put in to action. "There should be a clear perception, through careful quantification of costs and benefits that will accrue to society at large, of the desirability and justifiability of each [development] project. The adverse impact on affected families -economic, environment, social and cultural-needs to be assessed in a participatory and transparent manner" [14]. It further mentions that "The aim should be to minimize large scale displacement, as far as possible. Only the minimum area of land commensurate with the purpose of the project may be acquired. Also, as far as possible, projects may be setup on waste lands, degraded land or un-irrigated land. Acquisition of agricultural land for non-agricultural I the project may be kept to the minimum; multi- cropped land may be avoided to the extent possible for such purposes, and acquisition of irrigated land, if un avoidable, may be kept to the minimum." [15].

The inclusive growth that we speak more now should take care of the interests of the affected poor and marginalized sections. More transparency in initiation, voluntary consent based on local self determination and proper resettlement should receive great recognition and priority in the management of SEZs.

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S.No	State/ Place	Proponent	Type	Area	Problems
1	Barnala, Punjab	Triedent Group	SEZ	152 Hectares	Farmers angry because government procured fertile
2	Mundra, Gujarat	Adani Group	SEZ	2,428 ha for SEZ	Supreme court has stopped both projects because of a lock of
3	Raigadh, Maharashtra	Reliance, India Bulls	SEZ	14, 164 ha and 2,428ha	Government claims 50000 people will be affected by this
4	Mangalore, Karnataka	Oil And Natural Gas Corporation	Petrochemical SEZ	78.4 ha .acquired for phase I: 931 ha needed for Phase II	opposition is against acquisition of fertile land and Faulty EIA. MOEF"s export committee on
5	Amritsar, Punjab	DLF	SEZ		Fertile land acquired cheap
6	Barmer, Rajasthan	Jindal Group	Lignite mining/Pow	8000ha	Land acquisition less than market price, R&R package bad, Water
* 7	Gurgaon, Haryana	Reliance industries	SEZ	10117 ha original:440 ha notified	Land Acquisition . Farmers who have already sold their land want better compensation. Others
8	Shivnath river, Chhattisgarh	Radius Water Company	Water supply to industry	23.6 km stretch	protest against privatization
9	Bastar, Chhattisgarh	Tata Steel	Steel plant	2,063.06 ha	Land acquisition
10	Chamalpur, Karnataka	Power Company of Karnataka	Coal-Fire power plant	971 ha	Displacement of 13000 people has evoked strong protest. Impacts Nagarhole and Bandipur
11	Chamba, Himachal Pradesh	HulNala-i-II	small hydro		Gaddis and Gjjars oppose project due to loss of grazing grounds

2	Chhattisgarh	Indian Farmers Fertiliser Co-operative Limited, Chattisgarh	Thermal Power Station	750 ha	Tribals of the area have resisted any acquisition of land
13	Maharashtra	Videocan	SEZ	2.428 ha	protest by farmers against acquisition of land has forced the government not to acquire
14	Kerala	Kerala State Electricity Board	Hydropower project	163 MW	protest by environmental activists and member of the
15	Himachal Pradesh	Alfred Ford	ski village	54 ha	inadequate EIA
16	Himachal Pradesh	Jaypee	Dam: 1,000 mw power plant	Three sites considered	faulty EIA , shrine submergence
17	Jharkhand	Arector Mittal	steel plant	Three sites considered	Tribal communities living in the site areas protest land
18	Pondicherry	Subhash Projects and Marketing Limited, DS	port; 20 MT cargo handling capacity		Opposition to land acquisition; beach erosion ; livelihood of fisherfolk.protests force
19	Tamil Nadu	Tata group	Titanium di- Oxide plant	4856 ha	The Nadar community have opposed this project due to poor R&D track record of other such

20	Uttarkhand		slew of hydro power projects on the river Ganga and its		No water flow study: landslide-prone area: displacement . A fast by noted environmentalist G D Aggarwal has prompted administration to scrap 2 projects
21	Sikkim		slew of hydro power projects		Protests force government to scrap seven projects
22	Meghalaya	UCIL	Uranium Mining	351 ha	opposition by affected community as well as the
23	Jharkhand	r			Uranium Corporation of India limited (UCIL) has wreaked
24	Kakinada, Andhra Pradesh	ONGC, infrastructure Leasing & Financial Services	SEZ	4, 133 ha	Acquiring fertile land
25	Kerala	Harrison Malayam	Plantation		close to 10,000 Tribals and Dalits have occupied rubber
26	Arunachal Pradesh	NHPC	Dam: Multi purpose Dam		Faulty EIA. Locals oppose it on environmental issues . Downstream impact not
27	Arunachal Pradesh	Jaypee	Dam; 1,000 MW power plant		Faulty EIA. Locals oppose it on environmental issues . Downstream impact not
28	Arunachal & Assam	NHPC	Multi purpose Dam		Faulty EIA. Locals oppose it on environmental issues .
29	Manipur	NEEPCO	Multi purpose Dam	27,242 ha reservoir; 401.25 MW plant	No Prior informed consent from the villagers; faulty EIA
30	West Bengal	Tata Motors	small car plant	404 ha	Violent acquisition of land
31	West Bengal	Salim group, West Bengal Industrial Development	Chemical SEZ	5,665.6 ha	Resistance against acquisition of fertile agricultural land; violent clashes

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